

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

MACROECONOMIC DIMENSIONS OF THE ALTERNATIVE ECONOMICS

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Abstract

Today, the traditional profit-oriented economy and monetary evaluation continue to dominate the global economy. In contrast, the characteristics of an alternative economy prioritize people and their needs. This approach considers ecological limits, advocates for the thoughtful use of resources, and employs social, ecological, and needs-based strategies. It emphasizes democratic decision-making, cooperation based on collectivism, hierarchy-free relationships, solidarity, and a non-profit orientation rather than a focus on individual profit maximization.

The alternative economy shifts the emphasis from monetary assessments of activities to human-centric dimensions, advocating for public participation in decision-making processes that impact the well-being of regions, communities, and countries. Consequently, well-being is measured not solely by GDP, but through alternative indicators that, along with GDP, express macroeconomic parameters, integrating the principles of the alternative economy.

To accurately characterize the diverse dimensions of economic life and the environment, it is essential to develop multiple key macro-indicators. The combination of these indicators should provide a comprehensive understanding of the true state of development and progress within countries.

Keywords: *traditional economy, sustainable development, Alternative economy, social economy, macroeconomics*

Introduction

In the modern era, in contrast to traditional mainstream economic growth theory, demand is increasing, and alternative economic models are emerging. Today's economic system faces significant social challenges, including inequality within and between countries, poverty, environmental neglect, and pollution. Alternative economic models seek to tackle these issues by reforming the economic system. Each model, however, has different focal points and requires distinct measures to achieve its objectives.

Despite their variations, all alternative forms of economy share a common call for a paradigm shift within society, necessitating new structural changes and revised framework conditions. While each alternative approach has its unique advantages, there are also inherent limitations that currently hinder their widespread implementation.

Characteristics of the Alternative Economy

An alternative economy is a multidimensional economic system that, unlike the traditional economy, emphasizes social, ethical, and environmental goals alongside or instead of profit maximization. Unlike the neoclassical approach, which strictly separates ethics, responsibility, and humane business behaviors from economics, the alternative economy proposes reintegration with the solidarity and social aspects of the green and circular economy. This approach presents a universal economic perspective with humane business goals, humanizing the economy and better organizing economic and social life based on rationality, reason, and high human values.

Traditional economic mainstreaming is characterized by features such as specialization, economies of scale, competition, neglect of social and cultural requirements, agglomeration, growth and export orientation, private ownership, ecological unsustainability, and crisis management. In contrast, the alternative economy emphasizes diversification, small-scale production, social inclusion, cooperatives, decentralization, viability orientation, autonomy, local ownership, local market orientation, long-term investment value, community control, and environmental sustainability (1).

Social economics examines the ethical and social dimensions of economic behavior and institutions, advocating justice and the common good. It focuses on organizations such as cooperatives, non-profits, and social enterprises that prioritize social goals over economic benefits or profits. The social economy is built on the solidarity economy, which promotes economic democracy, social justice, and environmental sustainability through cooperative and community-based economic practices. Initiatives include fair trade, employment, well-being, community support for agricultural development, and financing gender-based enterprises and startups. It is related to the collaborative economy, which is based on mutual cooperation, joint production, consumption, and knowledge sharing. Participatory Economics (Parecon) proposes a participatory decision-making system in economic planning, giving employees and consumers institutional power in production and distribution decisions.

These forms significantly contribute to the development of the green economy, which aims at sustainable development without environmental degradation by reducing environmental risks. A green economy prioritizes environmental sustainability and social equity, supporting practices that protect the environment and reduce inequality. It aligns with the circular economy, which minimizes waste and maximizes resource use through reusing, repairing, renewing, and recycling materials and products, helping restore ecological balance. Implementing these goals often involves the digital economy and various technological platforms.

Alternative economic models address issues such as inequality, environmental sustainability, and social cohesion, organizing economic activities to meet the needs of people, communities, and countries in different ways. These characteristics form the core of the alternative economy system.

Alternative economic models differ from traditional neoclassical economic theory by offering different management approaches. They can be thought of as behavioral economics, which integrates psychological insights into economic theory to explain irrational decisions and how these decisions alter classical economic regularities. Ecological economics emphasizes the relationship between the economy and natural ecosystems, focusing on sustainability. Feminist economics examines economic issues from a gender perspective, advocating for equal valuation of women's work and fairer economic policies. Institutional economics focuses on the role of institutions in influencing economic behavior, emphasizing the importance of historical, social, and cultural factors.

Thus, the distinguishing features of the alternative economy prioritize people and their needs, consider ecological limits, require thoughtful resource use, and employ social, ecological, and needs-based approaches. They promote democratic decision-making, collectivism, cooperation based on free relations and solidarity, and non-commercial orientation instead of profit maximization. The alternative economy emphasizes human dimensions over monetary evaluations and encourages public participation in decision-making processes affecting the welfare of regions, communities, and countries. It is a broad and diverse field, with each approach offering unique insights and solutions to economic challenges. These approaches often intersect and complement each other, providing a richer understanding of economic phenomena and contributing to more inclusive and sustainable economic policies.

The weak institutional side of the modern economy is the lack of legal requirements in countries to implement these principles, resulting in the dominance of traditional, profit-oriented economic practices and development evaluations based on monetary factors.

Concepts of Alternative Economy

Today, several concepts can be considered alternative economic forms. Some theoretical alternatives suggest preserving the market economy but with specific regulatory measures and a new prioritization of goals and values. Others reject the market economy altogether and advocate a fundamentally different way of

doing business. These alternative economic models reflect various perspectives and solutions that aim to address the limitations and failures of traditional economic theories.

Representatives of these concepts discuss alternative economics based on a fundamental understanding of different perspectives and methodologies. What is common among them is that these different economic models, focusing on sustainability, equity, and social justice, often conflict with the assumptions of traditional economic theories.

The literature suggests that continuous economic growth is unsustainable and that a shift in focus to a sustainable economy prioritizing well-being over GDP growth is necessary (2). A stable economy, where economic activity is balanced by ecological limits, presents a paradigmatic solution to traditional economic growth theory (3). Continuous economic growth is thermodynamically unsustainable due to the inevitable depletion of natural resources (4). An alternative to the growth-oriented economic model is one where the functioning of the economy is determined by how well it provides the social conditions of the people (5). By reducing consumption and production, it is possible to create a more sustainable and fair society (6,7). Reducing consumption does not necessarily mean a reduction in the quality of life but can lead to an increase in well-being. However, this requires radical changes in daily life and attitudes towards the value of money and work. Economic management should not focus on growth; instead, it is necessary to develop appropriate policies and strategies to achieve sustainability and prosperity (8). The transition to a post-growth economy and environmental constraints must be implemented due to resource depletion (9).

Researchers and their papers highlight the limitations and potential harms of continued economic growth, advocating for alternative models that prioritize environmental sustainability, social equity, and long-term prosperity over GDP growth. These theories view economic growth as the cause of the prevailing challenges of the 21st century, such as social inequality and environmental problems. Economic growth is not a solution to social, ecological, and humanitarian problems. The contributions of these and other authors form the basis of various movements and schools of thought in alternative economics.

Accordingly, the issue arises of a new model of well-being that is not related to income growth. The new paradigm is an ethical economic model that places the environment and human well-being as primary goals, replacing competition and profit maximization with humane values that promote the growth of the common good (10). It forms the basis of human dignity, solidarity, justice, ecological sustainability, and values of transparency and collective decision-making. A good economy is an alternative economic system to the capitalist market economy because it does not prioritize profit, material wealth, concentration of power, or competition. Instead, the actors of the alternative economy emphasize the importance of the common good, values, trust, and cooperation.

With such approaches, well-being is no longer measured only by GDP but by alternative indicators that consider social and environmental factors, such as ecological security, equality, justice, and national happiness.

Conclusion

An important issue parallel to defining the principles of the alternative economy is integrating the Sustainable General Economic Welfare Development Indicator (ISEW) into the national reporting system. Alongside GDP, it should express macroeconomic parameters that incorporate elements of the alternative economy. Additionally, the Real Progress Indicators Index (GPI) should be developed. However, these alone will not fully capture the diverse dimensions of economic life and the environment, including economic, social development, ethical, environmental requirements, and justice, all characteristics of an alternative economy. Thus, developing a comprehensive set of main macro-indicators to determine the real state of development and progress of countries is essential.

References:

1. Mario Campana, Andreas Chatzidakis, Mikko Laamanen (2017), Introduction to the Special Issue: A Macromarketing Perspective on Alternative Economies, *Journal of Macromarketing*, March 2017, DOI: 10.1177/0276146717700228, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/315629175_Introduction_to_the_Special_Issue_A_Macromarketing_Perspective_on_Alternative_Economies
2. Tim Jackson (2017), "Prosperity Without Growth: Foundations for the Economy of Tomorrow", https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320182529_Prosperty_without_Growth_Foundations_for_the_Economy_of_Tomorrow
3. Herman E. Daly (1977), "Steady-State Economics", <http://pombo.free.fr/daly1991.pdf>; Joshua Farley, (2005) "Ecological Economics: Principles and Applications", https://www.academia.edu/21410975/Ecological_Economics_Principles_And_Applications
4. Nicholas Georgescu-Roegen (1971), "The Entropy Law and the Economic Process", Harvard University Press, https://content.csbs.utah.edu/~lozada/Adv_Resource_Econ/En_Law_Econ_Proc_Cropped_Optimized_Clearscan.pdf
5. Kate Raworth (2017), Doughnut Economics: Seven Ways to Think Like a 21st Century Economist Conference Paper in Regional and Business Studies, April 2020, DOI: 10.33568/rbs.2409, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340685996_Kate_Raworth_-_Doughnut_Economics_Seven_Ways_to_Think_Like_a_21st_Century_Economist_2017.
6. Giorgos Kallis (2015), "Degrowth: A Vocabulary for a New Era" (2015), https://www.academia.edu/16976529/Degrowth_A_Vocabulary_for_a_New_Era;
7. Giuseppe Feola, Leonie Guerrero Lara, Jacob Smessaert, Julia Spanier (2020), Book Review: The Case for Degrowth, *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions* 37:381-382, DOI:10.1016/j.eist.2020.10.006, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/346345495_Book_Review_The_Case_for_Degrowth.
8. Peter Victor (2008), "Managing Without Growth: Slower by Design, Not Disaster" (2008), Edward Elgar, Cheltenham, UK, Northampton, MA, USA, <https://www.zeeli.pro.br/wp-content/uploads/2012/06/LIVRO-Peter-VICTOR-Managing-without-growth.pdf>
9. Richard Heinberg (2011), "The End of Growth: Adapting to Our New Economic Reality", <https://richardheinberg.com/bookshelf/the-end-of-growth-book>
10. Christian Felber and Gus Hagelberg, „Economy for the Common Good“, <https://thenextsystem.org/sites/default/files/2017-08/FelberHagelberg.pdf>